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Organisational Justice, Attitude To Work And Productivity Of Academic Staff In Kebbi State Tertiary Institutions, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between organizational justice, attitudes to work, and productivity of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Using a descriptive correlational design, the study sampled 286 academic staff across six state-owned tertiary institutions. Data was collected through a validated and reliable questionnaire, covering four dimensions of organizational justice (distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational), six aspects of attitudes to work (job satisfaction, commitment, involvement, trust, motivation, and engagement), and five measures of productivity (teaching performance, research output, supervision of students, community service, and administrative duties). The findings revealed a moderate level of organizational justice and a high level of attitude to work among academic staff. Procedural justice exhibited the strongest positive correlation with productivity, while job satisfaction showed no significant relationship with productivity. Overall, organizational justice and attitudes to work were found to significantly predict academic staff productivity, accounting for 52.6% of the total variation. The study underscores the critical role of fair decision-making processes, staff engagement, and motivation in enhancing teaching, research, and administrative outputs. The results suggest that fostering a fair, supportive, and transparent work environment can significantly enhance academic productivity, contributing to the overall goals of tertiary education in Nigeria. Recommendations include improving procedural justice, fostering staff engagement, and providing resources for community and administrative roles to ensure sustainable productivity.

Keywords: Organisational Justice, Attitude to Work, Productivity, Academic Staff

INTRODUCTION

The notion of organizational justice is crucial in influencing employee attitudes and overall productivity within organizations (Auf et al., 2019). Recognized as a fundamental aspect of workplace dynamics, organizational justice has been a prominent focus in recent studies due to its significant role in enhancing employee attitudes and organizational commitment, which directly affect productivity levels (Colquitt et al., 2018). Defined as employees' perceptions of fairness within an organization (Choi, 2011), organizational justice fosters trust, strengthens commitment, and ultimately improves performance and productivity (Bonau, 2022; Zulkarnain, 2024).

This concept holds particular importance in Nigerian tertiary institutions, where socio-economic conditions and institutional policies play a significant role in shaping the motivation, morale, and productivity of academic staff. These individuals are key players in research, teaching, and the delivery of

quality education. However, the education sector in Nigeria, especially in Kebbi State, faces significant hurdles, such as chronic underfunding, inadequate infrastructure, and escalating workloads (Zulkarnain, 2024). These issues often amplify perceptions of inequity, negatively affecting the productivity and performance of academic personnel.

Perceptions of organizational justice significantly impact the attitudes of academic staff toward their roles. Research suggests that when academic staff perceive fairness in recognizing and rewarding their efforts, job satisfaction increases, leading to greater productivity (Christianah & Olufunmilola, 2023; Salau et al., 2018). Conversely, perceived injustice often results in disengagement and reduced motivation, adversely impacting productivity (Auf et al., 2019; Salau et al., 2021). Consequently, understanding the relationship between organizational justice, work attitudes, and productivity is vital to cultivating a motivated and efficient academic workforce. Creating supportive work environments that prioritize fairness and recognition is especially critical in reducing stressors and fostering higher productivity (Ike et al., 2019; Okolocha et al., 2021).

Institutional policies also play a pivotal role in shaping perceptions of organizational justice. Fair and equitable policies can significantly improve the morale of academic staff, enhancing their commitment to teaching and research (Christianah & Olufunmilola, 2023; Okolocha et al., 2021). Implementing such policies is essential for addressing the distinct challenges faced by academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, thereby boosting their job satisfaction and productivity.

The productivity of academic staff is integral to national development, as tertiary institutions are critical drivers of education and research that underpin progress. However, ongoing issues such as inadequate resources and unfair treatment of academic staff continue to impede these efforts (Zulkarnain, 2024). By exploring how organizational justice influences attitudes and productivity, policymakers and institutional leaders can craft strategies to establish equitable and supportive work environments. These measures can improve both individual and institutional outcomes, fostering the sustainable development of Nigeria's education sector (Auf et al., 2019).

With this in mind, the current study seeks to examine the relationship between organizational justice, work attitudes, and productivity among academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Academic institutions are widely regarded as organizations with the highest standards of integrity, where operations are conducted as expected and fairness is ensured across all areas. The administration of justice within an organization significantly influences employees' attitudes toward their work. In essence, employees' perception of fairness within their organization is a key determinant of their work attitudes. Social scientists emphasize that organizational justice should be considered the "first virtue of social institutions" due to its critical role in effective organizational management (Choi, 2011).

Tertiary educational institutions, being labor-intensive, rely heavily on their workforce for the effective delivery of services and the achievement of institutional objectives (Hettiararchchi and Jayarathna, 2014). These institutions depend on academic staff to fulfill their responsibilities in teaching, research, community engagement, and the creation and dissemination of knowledge. For these goals to be achieved, management must ensure that academic staff maintain positive attitudes toward their work in all areas of operation.

However, a concerning issue in recent years within tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, as noted by researchers, is the prevalence of poor attitudes among academic staff. This problem is evidenced by high turnover rates, increased intentions to leave, a lack of trust in supervisors and senior management, reduced commitment to teaching and other academic responsibilities, and feelings of being overworked and underappreciated. These conditions have led to demoralization, strong job dissatisfaction, and withdrawal behaviors. Psychological withdrawal manifests as daydreaming or disengagement during work, while physical withdrawal is evident in behaviors such as slowed work pace, extended breaks, tardiness, early departures, absenteeism, and unauthorized time off. Additionally, many academic staff exhibit reduced job involvement and even retaliatory behaviors for perceived injustices.

The root of these issues can be attributed to a perceived lack of organizational justice among academic staff. If this problem remains unaddressed, it could significantly hinder the productivity of academic staff,

putting the future of tertiary education in Kebbi State at serious risk. Academic staff play a critical role in ensuring the quality of education, and their productivity directly impacts the ability of institutions to produce competent, self-reliant, and competitive individuals who contribute to national and individual development. Without addressing issues of fairness, the goal of delivering quality education and fostering development in all spheres of life is unlikely to be achieved.

Given this context, the current study seeks to explore the impact of organizational justice on the productivity of academic staff by examining its influence on their attitudes toward work. A review of the literature revealed a lack of prior research specifically linking organizational justice, employee attitudes, and productivity within tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. This gap underscores the need for the present study to fill this critical void.

Objectives

The aim of the study is to examine the impact of organisational justice and attitudes to work on the productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions, Nigeria. While the following are the main objectives of the study:

- i. To study the level of organizational justice, attitudes to work and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions
- ii. To establish the relationship between organizational justice and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions
- iii. To establish the relationship between attitude to work and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions
- iv. To examine the influence of organizational justice and attitudes to work on productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of organizational justice, attitudes to work and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions?
- ii. Is there a significant relationship between organizational justice and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions?
- iii. Is there a significant relationship between attitude to work and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions?
- iv. Do organizational justice and attitudes to work influence productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions?

Research Hypotheses

Ho1: there is no significant relationship between organizational justice and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions

Ho2: there is no significant relationship between attitude to work and productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions

Ho3: there is no significant influence of organizational justice and attitudes to work on productivity of academic staff in Kebbi state tertiary institutions

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical review

This study reviewed Equity theory, Expectancy Theory, and Social Exchange Theory to provide a robust framework for understanding the dynamics of employee attitudes and behaviors.

Equity Theory

Adams (1963) developed Equity Theory to explain how perceptions of fairness in the workplace influence employee attitudes and productivity. According to this theory, employees evaluate their job satisfaction and motivation by comparing the perceived balance between their contributions (inputs) and the rewards they receive (outputs) with those of others. This framework is particularly relevant in educational institutions, where teaching staff may assess their efforts in relation to the rewards they receive, such as salaries, recognition, or institutional support.

The theory provides insights into how fairness in policies, rewards, and resource allocation impacts the attitudes and productivity of teaching staff in tertiary institutions. Studies show that when employees perceive inequity, it can result in reduced motivation and lower productivity (Baec & Shin, 2017). For instance, if academic staff feel their efforts are undervalued or inadequately rewarded compared to their colleagues, their attitudes toward their work may decline, ultimately affecting their performance (Baec & Shin, 2017).

Furthermore, the connection between organizational justice and employee attitudes can be effectively explained through Equity Theory. Fair treatment within an organization creates a positive work environment that enhances employee commitment and performance (Lambert & Hogan, 2013). This highlights the importance of equitable practices in fostering motivation and productivity among teaching staff.

Expectancy Theory

Expectancy Theory, introduced by Vroom (1964), describes how motivation is shaped by an individual's belief that their efforts will lead to performance and result in desirable rewards. The theory posits that employees are motivated to act in specific ways based on the anticipated outcomes of their actions. For instance, educators are more likely to engage positively with their work if they believe their efforts will lead to meaningful outcomes, such as student success or institutional recognition (Roch et al., 2019).

This theory provides a framework for understanding how the productivity of teaching staff is influenced by their expectations of rewards tied to their efforts, which are often shaped by their perceptions of organizational justice. When educators perceive a clear connection between their efforts and the rewards they receive, their motivation and productivity tend to increase (Chen et al., 2022). Moreover, research supports the idea that perceived organizational support boosts employee motivation and performance by establishing clear expectations and recognizing individual contributions (Chen et al., 2022). This highlights the importance of aligning organizational justice with reward systems to enhance the motivation and effectiveness of teaching staff.

Social Exchange Theory

Theory emphasizes the reciprocal relationship between employees and organizations, suggesting that when employees perceive fairness and justice, they are more likely to respond with positive attitudes and improved productivity (Blau, 1964). The attitudes and productivity of teaching staff are significantly shaped by their perceptions of organizational justice and support (Liaquat & Mehmood, 2017). For example, when educators feel that their institution prioritizes their well-being and professional development, they are more inclined to reciprocate through greater organizational citizenship behaviors and heightened engagement in their roles (Idrus, 2023).

Research consistently demonstrates that positive exchanges between employees and organizations result in improved attitudes and behaviors, while negative exchanges lead to diminished motivation and increased intentions to leave (Gould-Williams, 2007; Reader et al., 2016).

The integration of Equity Theory, Expectancy Theory, and Social Exchange Theory provides a well-rounded perspective on how organizational justice impacts the attitudes and productivity of teaching staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. By creating a fair and supportive work environment, these institutions can boost staff motivation and performance, ultimately improving educational outcomes for students.

Conceptual Review

Organisational Justice

Justice has long been regarded as one of humanity's fundamental needs, serving as the foundation for the existence and harmony of human societies (Iqbal et al., 2017). Choi (2011) emphasized the importance of justice as a key component in understanding organizational behavior. According to Adams (1965), justice pertains to individuals' perceptions of the fairness of decisions and policymaking processes within organizations and how these perceptions influence behavior. Similarly, Yean and Yosuf (2016) defined justice as the moral correctness of management's decisions and actions, guided by ethical standards, religious principles, or legal frameworks.

Organizational justice specifically relates to employees' perceptions of fair treatment within their organization (Wang et al., 2015). Kivimaki (2004) described organizational justice as the degree to which employees perceive workplace procedures, interactions, and outcomes as fair. Iqbal et al. (2017) further explained that organizational justice reflects employees' perceptions of fairness and their reactions to the outcomes they experience while working in an organization. These perceptions can significantly influence employees' attitudes and behaviors, ultimately impacting performance, commitment, and the overall success of the organization (Ajala, 2015).

Components of Organisational Justice

Scholars have categorized organizational justice into four distinct dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, informational justice, and interpersonal justice (Syarifat, 2016; Colquitt, 2001). Each of these dimensions plays a critical role in shaping employees' sense of fairness and their responses within the workplace.

Distributive Justice

Distributive justice pertains to employees' subjective assessments of how fairly outcomes such as wages, promotions, job roles, and workloads are distributed within an organization (Colquitt et al., 2001). It addresses the question, "How fair is what I receive for my work?" (Ajala, 2015). Kalay (2016) defines distributive justice as the equitable sharing of organizational outcomes among employees.

According to Ajala (2015), employees use three primary rules to evaluate the fairness of their outcomes. The first is the "equity" rule, which involves rewarding employees in proportion to their contributions. The second is the "equality" rule, which ensures that all employees receive approximately the same compensation. The third is the "need" rule, which allocates benefits based on individual requirements.

This understanding highlights that organizational justice involves an evaluative process wherein employees assess administrative decisions based on factors such as task distribution, adherence to schedules, empowerment, wage fairness, award allocation, equitable access to economic and social working environments, and transparency in internal decision-making processes (Iqbal et al., 2017). These factors collectively shape employees' perceptions of fairness within their workplace.

Procedural Justice

Procedural justice pertains to employees' perceptions of the fairness of the policies and procedures implemented by management to arrive at decision outcomes (Colquitt, 2001). According to Barsky et al. (2011), employees within organizations tend to respond emotionally to the fairness of these procedures, as well as the distribution of resources and rewards. These perceptions ultimately influence various organizational outcomes, including employee satisfaction, productivity, attitudes, and loyalty. Ajala (2015) identified six key criteria for determining whether a procedure is just:

1. **Consistency:** All employees are treated equally.
2. **Lack of Bias:** No individual or group is subjected to discrimination or preferential treatment.
3. **Accuracy:** Decisions are based on reliable and accurate information.
4. **Representation:** Relevant stakeholders are given the opportunity to provide input into the decision-making process.
5. **Correction:** Mechanisms, such as appeals processes, are in place to address and correct errors.
6. **Ethics:** Professional norms and standards of conduct are upheld.

In essence, procedural justice addresses the question, "How fair is the process that leaders use to make decisions?"

Interpersonal justice

Interpersonal justice, as described by Ajala (2015), involves treating employees with dignity, courtesy, and respect. Pracha et al. (2017) similarly define it as the unbiased admiration and regard an employee receives from their supervisor. Additionally, informational justice, closely related to interpersonal justice, refers to the provision of adequate information and fostering meaningful social interaction between supervisors and employees.

Kalay (2016) highlights the critical role of kindness, respect, and esteem in interpersonal relationships, particularly those between employees and their managers. Ajala (2015) further explains that interpersonal

justice is evident when decision-makers treat individuals with respect and sensitivity, while also thoroughly explaining the rationale behind their decisions.

In essence, interpersonal justice addresses the question, "To what extent do leaders treat employees with dignity, respect, and emotional support?" By fostering such an environment, organizations can create a more inclusive and respectful workplace that strengthens relationships and enhances employee morale.

Informational Justice

Syarifah (2016) described informational justice as the perception of fairness regarding a decision maker's truthfulness and the adequacy of their justifications for decisions. Kalay (2016) emphasized that informational justice involves providing employees with accurate and thorough information in organizational decision-making. According to Ajala (2015), informational justice pertains to being truthful and offering sufficient explanations, particularly when situations go awry. Similarly, Cropanzano and Molina (2015) explained that informational justice involves providing relevant evidence and explanations, which becomes especially crucial when things go wrong. Informational justice addresses the question, "Is the information used for decision-making shared equitably?"

Attitude

Fishbein and Ajzen (1974) defined attitude as a learned, positive or negative mental state of readiness, shaped by experience, which influences a worker's reactions to co-workers, objects, and situations. This suggests that an employee's behavior and responses at the workplace depend on their internal feelings, which can be either positive or negative (Ogilo et al., 2020). Hettiararchchi and Jayarathna (2014) argued that personal attitudes reflect the broad values held by an individual, shaping their opinions, prejudices, and judgment. Attitude is also described as a consistent tendency to react in a particular manner, whether positive or negative, toward a person, group, job, situation, object, or event (Cristina, 2015).

In the workplace context, Leonard (2018) defined job attitude as a predisposition to behave in certain ways due to personal experience and personality. Inuwa et al. (2017) viewed job attitude as employees' actions and inactions toward their work. Aries and Rizqi (2013) saw attitude toward work as the feelings employees have regarding different aspects of their work environment. Positive feelings indicate job satisfaction and enthusiasm to work, while negative feelings point to dissatisfaction and unfulfillment, leading to issues like insubordination, tardiness, absenteeism, and poor performance (Ogilo et al., 2020).

Various indicators of work attitude in organizations have been identified, such as job satisfaction, commitment, engagement, trust, involvement, and motivation (Ogilo et al., 2020; Milman, 2002; Choi, 2011). Thus, this study assessed the attitudes of academic staff based on these dimensions, as they are present in Kebbi State's tertiary institutions, illustrating the concept of 'attitude.'

Productivity

Employee productivity refers to how efficiently and effectively employees perform their work tasks (Morgan et al., 2021). It involves factors such as the time (presenteeism) or resources (performance) needed to complete tasks and the ability to solve problems in order to achieve goals (Indraswari & Martono, 2020). This productivity can be assessed by comparing an employee's output to that of others performing similar tasks or by measuring the number of units of a product or service produced within a set time (Awwad & Heyari, 2022). In higher education institutions, employee productivity is critical because it directly affects the institution's overall performance. Thus, academic staff productivity refers to how effectively and efficiently faculty members carry out their teaching, research, and service responsibilities (Awwad & Heyari, 2022). It is often measured as the total factor productivity of employees within a defined period in an organization (Morgan et al., 2021).

In higher education, academic staff productivity can be measured across several dimensions: teaching performance, research output, student supervision, community service, and administrative duties. Teaching performance is the ability of academic staff to deliver high-quality lectures, engage students, and enhance the overall learning experience (Biggs & Tang, 2022; Hénard & Roseveare, 2012). Research output refers to the quantity and quality of scholarly work, such as articles in respected journals, conference papers, books, and other research contributions (Cadez et al., 2017). According to Parkin (2016), student supervision involves guiding and mentoring students, including overseeing graduate theses and undergraduate research projects. Community service refers to involvement in activities that

benefit the community and industry, such as public lectures and outreach initiatives that support societal progress (Wanner, 2015). Administrative duties encompass the management of institutional responsibilities, including participation in committees, departmental activities, and governance roles (Jenkins, 2011).

Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1: Conceptual model of the relationship among organisational justice, attitude and academic staff productivity

Source: Researchers (2025)

Figure 1 shows the relationship among the variables of the study. It shows that the two arrows extending from the two independent variables (organizational justice and attitude to work) to the dependent variable indicate the direct effect of both organisational justice and attitude to work on academic staff productivity.

Empirical review

Various studies empirically established association existing among organisational justice, attitude to work and employee productivity. For example, Choi (2011) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between organizational justice and employee performance. The research focused on three dimensions of organizational justice: distributive, procedural, and interpersonal. Using hierarchical regression analysis, the study tested its hypotheses and found that all three dimensions of organizational justice positively influence employee performance. Similarly, Kalay (2016) explored the impact of organizational justice on employee performance, focusing on public school teachers in Turkey. The study employed partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) to test its hypotheses. The findings revealed that

distributive justice has a positive and significant effect on task performance. However, procedural justice and interactional justice were found to have no significant impact on task performance. Iqbal et al. (2017) also examined the influence of organizational justice on employee performance within Pakistan's public sector, specifically among employees of Pakistan Railways. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire administered to approximately 120 employees. The results showed that organizational justice significantly impacts employee performance.

Likewise, Ogilo et al. (2020) investigated the impact of employees' attitudes on organizational performance in service firms in Port Rivers State. Data were collected from 200 residents using a well-structured questionnaire and analyzed through regression analysis. The findings indicated that employees' attitudes significantly and positively influence organizational performance. Abdalkrim and Elhalim (2016) examined the effect of attitudes toward work on employee performance among non-Saudi academic staff in higher education institutions. Data were gathered through closed online questionnaires and analyzed using multiple regression techniques. The results revealed a significantly positive effect of work attitudes on the performance of non-Saudi academic staff. Rahiman and Kodikal (2017) conducted an empirical investigation into the impact of work attitudes on employee performance in the healthcare industry. Quantitative data were collected and validated using P-tests, F-tests, correlation, and regression analysis. The study demonstrated a significant relationship between employees' attitudes and their performance outcomes.

Khan et al. (2014) analyzed the effect of attitudes on employee performance in the textile industry in Punjab, Pakistan. Data were collected through a questionnaire, achieving an 83% response rate. The findings showed that attitudes toward work are positively associated with employee performance. Inuwa et al. (2017) explored the relationship between job attitudes and employee performance among non-academic staff at Bauchi State University, Gadau. The analysis revealed a positive and significant relationship between job attitudes and employee performance. Hettiararchchi and Jayarathna (2014) studied the influence of employee work-related attitudes on job performance within the tertiary and vocational education sectors in Sri Lanka. Their findings indicated that work-related attitudes have a significant impact on job performance, explaining 26.7% of the variance in job performance among employees in Sri Lanka's government sector. However, a thorough search for literature did not reveal any prior studies in Kebbi State institutions of higher learning, hence a to fill this void.

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative approach was employed for this study, using a descriptive correlational design. The target population consists of all academic staff from the tertiary institutions owned by Kebbi State, which include Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero; Kebbi State Polytechnic, Dakin-gari; Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu; Kebbi State School of Nursing and Midwifery; College of Health Science and Technology, Jega; and College of Basic and Advanced Studies, Yauri. These institutions were selected because they are owned and managed by the state. According to the registry offices of these institutions, there are approximately 1,000 academic staff, which constitutes the study population. A sample size of 286 was drawn using Slovin's formula [$n = N/1+N(e^2)$], to whom the questionnaire was administered. Cluster and simple random sampling methods were employed to select the respondents.

The research instrument used was a questionnaire, divided into four sections. Section A gathered personal information from the respondents, Section B focused on items related to organizational justice (independent variable I), Section C addressed the constructs of attitude toward work (independent variable II), and Section D contained items measuring academic staff productivity (dependent variable). The questionnaire was reviewed by a panel of experts, selected based on their experience, expertise, and administrative roles in academia, as well as their proficiency in measurement and evaluation, for validation purposes. Based on the feedback from the panel, modifications were made to the original instrument. The content validity index (CVI) was computed and yielded a value of 0.75, indicating the instrument's validity. The reliability of the questionnaire was determined by calculating Cronbach's alpha

using SPSS and pilot study data. All constructs achieved reliability scores above the benchmark of 0.7 (Amin, 2005).

Data will be collected from 286 respondents by distributing the questionnaires and requesting their responses. The data analysis will be conducted as follows: statistical means will be used to analyze the data related to objective one. For objectives two and three, Pearson’s product moment correlation (PPMC) coefficients will be used to examine the relationships among organizational justice, attitude toward work, and academic staff productivity. Finally, regression analysis will be employed to analyze the data for objective four.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Data was analysed based on the research questions/hypotheses earlier proposed, as presented below:

Research Question one: *What is the level of organizational justice, attitude to work and academic staff productivity in Kebbi state’s tertiary institutions?*

Level of Organisational Justice

Table 1: Mean on Organisational Justice

Organisational Justice	Mean	Interpretation
Distributive Justice	3.00	Moderate
Procedural Justice	2.99	Moderate
Interpersonal Justice	3.05	Moderate
Informational justice	3.01	Moderate
Grand Mean =	3.01	Moderate

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 1 displays the mean scores showing the degree of agreement among teaching staff on organizational justice across four dimensions: distributive justice, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, and informational justice. The mean scores for these dimensions range from 2.99 to 3.05. Interpersonal justice had the highest level of agreement with a mean score of 3.05, while procedural justice had the lowest, with a mean score of 2.99. The overall grand mean score for the four dimensions of organizational justice was 3.01, which, based on the scale used, reflects a moderate level of agreement. This suggests that the perceived administration of justice in Kebbi State's tertiary institutions is moderate.

Level of Attitude to Work

Table 2: Mean on Attitude to work

Attitude to Work	Mean	Interpretation
Job satisfaction	3.25	Moderate
Commitment	3.72	High
Involvement	3.63	High
Trust	3.34	Moderate
Motivation	3.86	High
Engagement	4.14	High
Overall Mean	3.66	High

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 2 presents the six dimensions that define attitude toward work as the independent variables in the study: job satisfaction, commitment, involvement, trust, motivation, and engagement. The table shows the mean scores representing the level of agreement among respondents regarding these six aspects of attitude toward work. The mean scores for these dimensions range from 3.25 to 4.14. Engagement had the highest level of agreement, with a mean score of 4.14, followed by motivation (mean = 3.86). Commitment ranked next with a mean score of 3.72, followed by involvement (mean = 3.63), trust (mean = 3.34), and job satisfaction (mean = 3.25). The overall mean score for the independent variable, attitude toward work, was 3.66, which, on the scale used, corresponds to "agree," indicating a favorable overall rating by the respondents. This suggests that academic staff in Kebbi State's tertiary institutions demonstrate a high level of positive attitude toward their work.

Level of Academic Staff Productivity

Table 3: Mean on Academic Staff Productivity

Organisational Justice	Mean	Interpretation
Teaching Performance	4.13	High
Research Output	3.45	High
Supervision of students	4.13	High
Community service	3.31	Moderate
Administrative duties	2.64	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.53	High

Source: Field Data (2025)

The dependent variable, academic staff productivity, was categorized into five constructs: teaching performance, research output, supervision of students, community service, and administrative duties. The items used to measure these constructs were rated on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 representing "strongly disagree" (the lowest level of agreement) and 5 representing "strongly agree" (the highest level).

According to Table 3, teaching performance received a mean score of 4.13, which corresponds to "agree" on the scale, reflecting a strong evaluation of staff teaching performance. Research output earned a mean score of 3.45, indicating a positive assessment of the academic staff's research productivity. Supervision of students also scored a mean of 4.13, aligning with "agree," which suggests a favorable evaluation of student supervision. In terms of community service, the mean score was 3.31, reflecting a moderate assessment of staff participation in community service activities. Lastly, administrative duties were rated with a mean score of 2.64, suggesting a moderate evaluation of academic staff's performance in administrative tasks.

The overall mean score for academic staff productivity was 3.53, which corresponds to "agree" on the scale, indicating a generally positive evaluation of academic staff productivity. This suggests that academic staff in Kebbi State's tertiary institutions demonstrate a high level of productivity.

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between organizational justice and academic staff productivity

Table 4: Correlation between the four components of organizational justice and academic staff productivity

Variables	Pearson's r	P-value	decision	interpretation
Academic Staff Productivity				
Distributive Justice	0.400	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant
Procedural Justice	0.601	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant
Interpersonal Justice	0.434	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant
Informational justice	0.523	P<0.01	Rejected	Significant

Source: Field Data (2025)

Table 4 displays the correlation results between the four dimensions of organizational justice and academic staff productivity. As shown in the table, academic staff productivity was positively and significantly correlated with distributive justice ($r = 0.400$, $p < 0.01$). It also showed a strong positive correlation with procedural justice ($r = 0.601$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, academic staff productivity was positively associated with interpersonal justice ($r = 0.434$, $p < 0.01$). Lastly, a significant positive correlation was found between academic staff productivity and informational justice ($r = 0.523$, $p < 0.01$).

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between attitude to work and academic staff productivity

Table 5: Correlation between the six components of attitude to work and academic staff productivity

Variables	Pearson's r	P-value	decision	interpretation
Academic Staff Productivity				
Job satisfaction	0.063	P<0.001	Not rejected	Insignificant
Commitment	0.601	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant
Involvement	0.550	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant
Trust	0.564	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant
Motivation	0.608	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant
Engagement	0.535	P<0.001	Rejected	Significant

Source: Field Data (2025)

To examine the relationship between each of the six constructs of the independent variable (attitude to work) and the dependent variable (academic staff productivity), Pearson’s linear correlation coefficient was applied at a 0.01 significance level with a two-tailed test. Table 5 presents the correlation results. As shown in the table, a significant positive relationship was found between commitment and staff productivity, with an r-value of 0.601 ($p < 0.01$). Involvement also showed a significant positive relationship with staff productivity, with an r-value of 0.550 ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, trust demonstrated a significant positive correlation with staff productivity, with a Pearson’s r-value of 0.564 ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, motivation was significantly positively correlated with staff productivity, with an r-value of 0.608 ($p < 0.01$). Engagement also exhibited a positive correlation with staff productivity ($r = 0.535$, $p < 0.001$). However, the correlation between job satisfaction and staff productivity was found to be insignificant, with a Pearson’s r-value of 0.062 ($p > 0.01$).

Ho3: There is no significant influence of organizational justice and attitude to work on academic staff productivity

Table 6: Regression analysis of the influence of organizational justice and attitude to work on academic staff productivity

	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient		Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	44.341	6.157		7.202	0.000
Organisational Justice	0.727	0.250	0.209	2.908	0.04
Attitude to Work	0.789	0.146	0.334	5.413	0.000

R = 0.698 , R2 = 0.526, F = 37.486

a. Dependent variable: Academic staff productivity

b. Predictor variables: Organisational justice and attitude to work

Table 6 presents the results of the regression analysis. As shown, the F-value of 37.486 indicates that both organizational justice and attitude to work are effective in explaining variations in academic staff productivity. The R-squared value of 0.526 reveals that the predictor variables together account for 52.6% of the total variation in productivity. This means that the remaining 47.4% of the variation is attributed to other factors not covered in this study.

The table also highlights that both organizational justice and attitude to work are significant and positive predictors of academic staff productivity, with $\beta_1 = 0.209$ ($p = 0.004$) for organizational justice and $\beta_1 = 0.334$ ($p = 0.000$) for attitude to work. These results suggest that organizational justice and attitude to work both have a significant and positive impact on academic staff productivity. Specifically, the coefficients indicate that organizational justice influences productivity by 20.9%, while attitude to work influences it by 33.4%. Therefore, both organizational justice and attitude to work significantly affect academic staff productivity in Kebbi State’s tertiary institutions.

DISCUSSION

The study’s findings on the level of organizational justice show that distributive justice, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, and informational justice all received moderate levels of agreement. This suggests a reasonable level of justice in the management of tertiary institutions. For distributive justice, the moderate level of agreement may be due to staff feeling reasonably rewarded for their contributions, receiving fairly equal compensation, and benefiting in line with personal needs. Similarly, the moderate level of agreement for procedural justice could reflect staff perceptions of a fair and consistent decision-making process employed by leaders. The moderate level of interpersonal justice might be attributed to the degree to which leaders treat staff with dignity, respect, and emotional support. Finally, the moderate level of informational justice could be explained by the fair sharing of information used in decision-making processes.

The findings on staff attitude to work revealed that engagement received the highest level of agreement. This could be attributed to several factors: staff feel energized and mentally resilient while working,

demonstrate a strong willingness to invest effort in their tasks, and show persistence even when facing challenges. They also experience a sense of significance, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge, with a deep focus on their work that makes time pass quickly and makes it difficult to detach from their tasks.

Motivation followed as the second-highest level of agreement, likely because staff are passionate about their jobs and invest considerable effort in achieving institutional goals. Similarly, commitment and involvement received high levels of agreement. Commitment may be driven by staff's emotional attachment to their institution, their perception of the costs and risks of leaving, and their sense of obligation and responsibility. Job involvement, on the other hand, might stem from staff's psychological identification with their work and the significance it holds in their lives.

However, trust and job satisfaction showed moderate levels of agreement. In the case of trust, this could be attributed to factors such as fair performance appraisals, equitable treatment, reasonable discipline, open communication, and the integrity of colleagues, supervisors, and management. For job satisfaction, the moderate agreement could reflect staff's moderate levels of pleasure or contentment with their job. Overall, the mean score for staff attitude to work indicates a high level of positive attitude, suggesting a reasonable degree of commitment and engagement among academic staff.

The findings on staff productivity revealed high levels of agreement on teaching performance, research output, and supervision of students. This indicates that academic staff are able to deliver high-quality lectures, engage students effectively, and significantly contribute to the overall learning experience. It also highlights the quality and quantity of staff scholarly work, including publications in reputable journals, conference papers, seminars, books, and other academic contributions. Additionally, the findings reflect a strong mentor-mentee relationship, with staff providing academic guidance and supervising graduate theses and undergraduate research projects.

The results also showed that community service and administrative duties received moderate levels of agreement. In terms of community service, staff involvement in community and industry activities, public lectures, and outreach initiatives was found to be at a fair level, contributing to societal development. Regarding administrative duties, academic staff were found to be moderately fulfilling their administrative responsibilities. Overall, the mean score for staff productivity indicates a high level of productivity, demonstrating that academic staff are highly productive in their roles at the institution.

The findings on the relationship between the four dimensions of organizational justice—distributive justice, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, and informational justice—and academic staff productivity show a positive correlation across all aspects. Overall, the study reveals a significant positive relationship between organizational justice and academic staff productivity, which aligns with previous research indicating a positive connection between organizational justice and employee productivity (Iqbal et al., 2017; Abdalkrim & Abd Elhalim, 2016; Choi, 2011).

Among the four dimensions, procedural justice had the strongest association with academic productivity. This finding is supported by Choi (2011), who also identified a significant positive link between procedural justice and employee productivity. The strong relationship can be attributed to respondents' relatively high perceptions of procedural justice, which reflects their belief in the fairness and consistency of the decision-making processes used by leaders. On the other hand, distributive justice showed the weakest association with academic staff productivity. This contrasts with Kalay (2016), who found a strong and positive relationship between distributive justice and employee performance. The difference in findings may stem from the distinct contexts of the studies: while John et al. conducted their research in profit-oriented organizations, this study focused on educational institutions, which have unique operational dynamics.

The findings on the relationship between attitude to work and academic staff productivity reveal a positive correlation. Five of the six constructs of attitude to work; commitment, trust, involvement, engagement, and motivation, were found to have a significant positive relationship with academic staff productivity, while job satisfaction was not significantly associated with productivity. Motivation exhibited the strongest association with academic staff productivity, aligning with Ogilo et al. (2020) findings that motivation in the workplace enhances competency development, leading to higher

productivity. The relationship between motivation and staff productivity in this study can likely be attributed to the institutions' ability to motivate staff, encouraging them to invest the necessary effort to achieve pre-determined goals.

Engagement, however, showed the weakest association with staff productivity. This may be due to the staff's positive, fulfilling work-related state of mind, characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption, which may not directly translate into productivity in this context. Job satisfaction, which was not significantly linked to staff productivity, may reflect unfavorable feelings or emotions with which staff view their work. This finding contrasts with the study by Hettiarachchi & Jayarathna (2014), which revealed a positive association between job satisfaction and employee productivity. The discrepancy between the two findings may be attributed to differences in the geographical and cultural contexts of the studies. While both studies were conducted in educational settings, the present study was carried out in Kebbi State, Nigeria, whereas Hettiarachchi & Jayarathna's research took place in a different country. These variations in context, particularly cultural factors, may influence how job satisfaction impacts productivity.

Furthermore, the findings on the influence of organizational justice and attitude to work on academic staff productivity revealed that the two predictor variables together account for 52.60% of the total variation in staff productivity. Specifically, organizational justice explains 20.9% of the variation, while attitude to work accounts for 33.4%. These results suggest that both organizational justice and attitude to work have a significant impact on academic staff productivity. This finding aligns with previous research, which also highlights the positive influence of organizational justice and attitude to work on employee productivity (Inuwa et al., 2017; Iqbal et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

The study underscores the significant role of organizational justice and attitudes to work in enhancing the productivity of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria. It reveals that while the perception of fairness in distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational justice is at a moderate level, such perceptions positively and significantly influence academic productivity. Procedural justice had the highest impact, indicating the importance of fair and consistent decision-making processes in driving productivity. Attitude to work also showed a high level of agreement among respondents, particularly in dimensions like engagement, motivation, and commitment, which were positively associated with productivity. However, job satisfaction showed no significant correlation with academic staff productivity, which may be influenced by contextual factors unique to the region.

Moreover, the study establishes that organizational justice and attitude to work collectively explain 52.6% of the variation in academic staff productivity, emphasizing their critical influence. Teaching performance, research output, and student supervision demonstrated high levels of productivity, while community service and administrative duties were rated moderately. These findings highlight the need for institutions to foster a supportive and fair work environment to optimize the potential of academic staff, thereby ensuring institutional and national development.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance organizational justice, attitudes to work, and the productivity of academic staff in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State, Nigeria:

1. **Enhance Procedural Justice:** Institutional management should ensure that decision-making processes are transparent, consistent, and inclusive. Stakeholders should be actively involved in decisions that impact their roles, and mechanisms for addressing grievances or correcting errors should be strengthened.
2. **Academic staff should be fairly rewarded** based on their contributions, responsibilities, and performance. Clear and equitable guidelines for distributing resources, promotions, and workload should be developed and communicated to all staff members.

3. Administrators should cultivate a culture of respect and dignity in interpersonal interactions. Clear, truthful, and adequate communication should be prioritized, especially when conveying decisions or changes that affect staff.
4. Institutions should implement programs to boost employee engagement, motivation, and commitment. This could include recognition for outstanding performance, opportunities for professional growth, and creating a work environment where staff feel valued and supported.
5. While job satisfaction was not significantly associated with productivity in this study, steps should still be taken to improve the working conditions, benefits, and overall morale of academic staff to avoid negative spillover effects on other productivity dimensions.
6. Policies and programs aimed at motivating staff should be enhanced, including incentives such as research grants, career development workshops, and performance-based promotions to encourage greater effort toward institutional goals.
7. To improve moderate ratings in community service and administrative duties, institutions should provide resources and support for faculty involvement in community initiatives and effective management of administrative responsibilities.
8. Management should periodically evaluate staff perceptions of organizational justice and attitudes to work through surveys and feedback mechanisms. This will help identify emerging issues and implement timely corrective actions.
9. Policymakers and institutional leaders should develop context-specific strategies that address the unique challenges of tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. For instance, cultural and regional considerations should be factored into the design of fairness and productivity-enhancing initiatives.

By addressing these areas, tertiary institutions in Kebbi State can create a more equitable and supportive environment that fosters positive work attitudes and maximizes academic staff productivity, contributing to the achievement of broader educational goals.

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